

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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PRIMARY BREAST MYXOFIBROSARCOMA MIMICKING DESMOID FIBROMATOSIS: A DIAGNOSTIC PITFALL AND SURGICAL MANAGEMENT OF A GIANT TUMOR

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Resume. Primary mixed fibrosarcoma of the breast is an extremely rare malignant mesenchymal tumour. We present the clinical case of a 55-year-old woman and describe a rapidly enlarging mass in the left breast measuring approximately 20 × 19 cm. The core-needle biopsy report suggested a diagnosis of desmoid fibromatosis. Radiological investigations revealed a fairly large, heterogeneous tumour occupying almost the entire breast. Given the locally advanced nature of the disease and the severe pain, the patient underwent surgical treatment — a mastectomy with axillary lymph node dissection. Histological examination revealed spindle-shaped tumour cells arranged in intersecting bundles within a pronounced myxoid matrix with a characteristic tortuous vascular pattern. Immunohistochemical examination confirmed the diagnosis of primary breast myxofibrosarcoma (G1) with negative surgical margins (R0). This report expands the limited literature on primary breast myxofibrosarcoma and highlights the need to consider rare sarcomas in the differential diagnosis of large spindle cell tumours of the breast.

Key words: myxofibrosarcoma, breast sarcoma, spindle cell tumor, diagnostic challenge.

ДЕСМОИД ФИБРОМАТОЗГА ТАҚЛИД ҚИЛУВЧИ БИРЛАШМАЛ КЎКРАК МИКСОФИБРОСАРКОМАСИ: ГИГАНТ ЎСМАНИНГ ДИАГНОСТИК ЧУҚУРИ ВА ЖАРРОҲЛИК ЙЎЛИ БИЛАН ДАВОЛАШ

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Резюме. Кўкрак безининг бирламчи миксофибросаркомаси ниҳоятда кам учрайдиган ёмон сифатли мезенхимал ўсма ҳисобланади. Ушбу мақолада 55 ёшли аёлда чап кўкрак безида тахминан 20 × 19 см ўлчамдаги тез ўсувчи ўсма ҳолати тасвирланган. Трусут (ядроли игна) биопсияси натижасида десмоид фиброматоз таъхиси қўйилган. Радиологик текширувлар деярли бутун кўкрак безини эгаллаган катта, гетероген ўсмани аниқлади. Касалликнинг маҳаллий тарқалганлиги ва кучли оғриқ синдроми туфайли беморга жарроҳлик даволаш — мастектомия ва қўлтиқ ости лимфа тугунларини диссекция қилиш амалиёти ўтказилди. Гистологик текширувда шпинделсимон ўсма ҳужайралари кесишувчи тутамлар кўринишида, яққол миксоид матрицада ва ўзига хос бурама томилар нақши билан жойлашгани аниқланган. Иммуногистокимёвий текширув натижасида кўкрак безининг бирламчи миксофибросаркомаси (G1) таъхиси тасдиқланди ва резекция четлари манфий (R0) эканлиги аниқланди. Ушбу клиник ҳолат кўкрак безининг бирламчи миксофибросаркомаси бўйича мавжуд чекланган илмий маълумотларни бойитади ҳамда йирик шпинделсимон ҳужайрали ўсмаларни дифференциал таъхислашда кам учрайдиган саркомаларни ҳам ҳисобга олиш зарурлигини таъкидлайди.

Калит сўзлар: миксофибросаркома, кўкрак беги саркомаси, шпинделсимон ҳужайрали ўсма, диагностика қийинчиликлар.

ПЕРВИЧНАЯ МИКСОФИБРОСАРКОМА МОЛОЧНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ, ИМИТИРУЮЩАЯ ДЕСМОИДНЫЙ ФИБРОМАТОЗ: ДИАГНОСТИЧЕСКАЯ ОШИБКА И ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОЕ ЛЕЧЕНИЕ ГИГАНТСКОЙ ОПУХОЛИ

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Резюме. Первичная миксофибросаркома молочной железы представляет собой чрезвычайно редкую злокачественную мезенхимальную опухоль. Представлен клинический случай 55-летней жен-

щины с быстро увеличивающимся образованием в левой молочной железе размером приблизительно 20×19 см. По результатам трепан-биопсии был установлен диагноз десмоидного фиброматоза. Радиологические исследования выявили крупную гетерогенную опухоль, занимающую практически всю молочную железу. С учетом местно-распространённого характера процесса и выраженного болевого синдрома пациентке было выполнено хирургическое лечение — мастэктомия с диссекцией подмышечных лимфатических узлов. Гистологическое исследование выявило веретеновидные опухолевые клетки, расположенные в перекрещивающихся пучках в выраженном миксоидном матриксе с характерным извитым сосудистым рисунком. Иммуногистохимическое исследование подтвердило диагноз первичной миксофибросаркомы молочной железы (G1) с отрицательными краями резекции (R0). Данный клинический случай дополняет ограниченные литературные данные о первичной миксофибросаркоме молочной железы и подчёркивает необходимость учитывать редкие саркомы в дифференциальной диагностике крупных веретенноклеточных опухолей молочной железы.

Ключевые слова: миксофибросаркома, саркома молочной железы, веретенноклеточная опухоль, диагностические трудности.

Introduction. Myxofibrosarcoma is a malignant fibroblastic soft-tissue tumour characterised by a myxoid stromal component, pleomorphic spindle-shaped cells and a characteristic tortuous vascular network. The tumour most commonly occurs in the extremities of elderly patients and is one of the most common sarcomas of this site in this age group. However, several cases of breast involvement have been described, which are extremely rare. Primary breast sarcomas account for less than 1% of all malignant tumours in this location and constitute a heterogeneous group of mesenchymal neoplasms with varying biological behaviour. Among these, mixofibrosarcoma is one of the least frequently described histological subtypes. Consequently, the rarity of the disease hinders the study of its clinical and pathological features and optimal treatment approaches. The diagnosis of breast myxofibrosarcoma presents significant difficulties. The clinical presentation is usually non-specific, and the results of imaging studies are often indistinguishable from other spindle-cell lesions of the breast, including phylloid tumours, desmoid fibromatosis and metaplastic carcinoma. Even core-needle biopsy does not always allow for a correct diagnosis due to the marked histological heterogeneity of the tumour. Given the extremely small number of reported cases listed in (Table 1), each new case is valuable for the consideration of the disease from diagnostic, surgical and clinical perspectives. This paper presents a case of giant primary mixofibrosarcoma of the breast, initially interpreted as desmoid fibromatosis on trephine biopsy, which demonstrates the potential for diagnostic errors and the specific features of surgical management of this rare condition.

Materials and methods. A clinical examination, ultrasound scan, CT scan and core needle biopsy were performed. Surgical treatment consisted of a mastectomy with axillary lymph node dissection. Histopathological and immunohistochemical examinations were used to establish the definitive diagnosis.

A 55-year-old woman presented to a specialist oncology centre complaining of a rapidly enlarging mass covering her entire left breast. According to the patient, the mass had been present since 2018 and had increased significantly in size over the previous six months. The patient reported severe pain and a sensation of heaviness due to the large size of the tumour. Physical examination revealed a giant tumour occupying almost the entire left breast. The mass measured approximately 20×19 cm, as shown in (Figure 1); the surface was irregular, and the tumour was firmly fixed to the surrounding tissues. The skin over the tumour was stretched and deformed. No ulceration or discharge from the nipple was observed. The initial ultrasound examination revealed a large, heterogeneous cystic-solid mass occupying almost the entire left breast, measuring approximately $212 \times 146 \times 199$ mm. Several additional hypoechoic foci were also detected in various quadrants of the breast. The right breast showed no structural changes. Subsequently, computed tomography confirmed the presence of a large, irregularly shaped tumour in the left breast with heterogeneous density and signs of contrast enhancement; characteristic radiological features are shown in Figure 2, indicating marked vascularisation. A core needle biopsy was performed prior to surgery. Histological examination of the biopsy material confirmed the presence of a poorly differentiated spindle-cell mesenchymal lesion, most consistent with desmoid fibromatosis. Due to the large size of the tumour, its progressive growth and pronounced clinical symptoms, a decision was made at a multidisciplinary consultation to proceed with surgical treatment. The patient underwent a left-sided mastectomy with axillary lymph node dissection. During the operation, the tumour was removed as a single en bloc specimen together with breast tissue and regional lymphatic structures. No macroscopic invasion of the pectoralis major muscle was identified during the operation. Macroscopic examination of the resected specimen revealed a large, heterogeneous tumour with a maximum diameter of approximately 20 cm. On section, the tumour was greyish-white in colour, resembling fish flesh, with areas of myxoid degeneration, cystic changes and focal haemorrhages. Microscopically, his-

topathological examination revealed spindle-shaped tumour cells arranged in intersecting bundles against a background of marked myxoid stroma. The tumour cells exhibited nuclear pleomorphism and mitotic activity. A characteristic tortuous vascular pattern was also observed. No signs of epithelial differentiation were detected. Based on the morphological and immunohistochemical examinations performed, the final diagnosis was established as primary mixofibrosarcoma of the breast (G1). The surgical margins were free from tumour infiltration (R0 resection). The postoperative period was uneventful, and the wound healed by primary tension. The patient was discharged in a satisfactory condition with a recommendation for further consultation with a radiotherapist.

Figure 1. Clinical appearance of the patient demonstrating a giant tumor occupying almost the entire left breast.

Figure 2. Computed tomography showing a large heterogeneous mass occupying the left breast with irregular contours.

Discussion. Myxofibrosarcoma is considered a malignant fibroblastic soft tissue sarcoma, characterised by variable cellularity, abundant myxoid stroma and characteristic active vascularisation. The most common site is the extremities in elderly patients, whilst primary breast involvement is extremely rare. Primary sarcomas localised in the breast account for less than 1% of all malignant tumours of this organ and constitute a heterogeneous group of mesenchymal neoplasms with varying prognostic features. Among these tumours, myxofibrosarcoma is one of the rarely described histological subtypes. The diagnosis of breast myxofibrosarcoma does not follow a specific algorithm due to the absence of specific clinical and radiological features. Patients usually present with a rapidly enlarging mass, which often reaches a considerable size by the time of diagnosis. Imaging techniques, such as ultrasound, mammography and computed tomography, allow the size of the tumour and the extent of local spread to be assessed. Unfortunately, however, they do not provide a reliable differential diagnosis between sarcoma and other spindle-cell tumours of the breast. In the present case, the tumour measured 20 × 19 cm, which is unusually large compared with previously described cases. Another important aspect of this observation was the discrepancy between the preoperative diagnosis, established on the basis of a core needle biopsy, and the final histopathological report. The biopsy material suggested desmoid fibromatosis, which highlights the potential limitations of small biopsy samples in heterogeneous spindle-cell tumours. Primary mixed fibrosarcoma of the breast is an extremely rare malignant mesenchymal tumour with non-specific clinical and radiological features. As demonstrated in the present case, preoperative diagnosis can be challenging, and core needle biopsy may lead to misinterpretation due to morphological similarities with other spindle-cell lesions, such as desmoid fibromatosis or metaplastic carcinoma. The primary treatment for primary breast sarcomas is radical resection of the tumour with negative resection margins. The infiltrative nature of the tumour's growth and the presence of heterogeneous microscopic tumour spread beyond the visible margins are responsible for the high rate of local recurrence. Therefore, achieving an R0 resection is considered the most important prognostic factor. Unlike epithelial breast tumours, lymph node metastasis is rare in sarcomas; therefore, routine axillary lymph node dissection is not recommended. However, in cases where the epithelial nature of the tumour cannot be reliably ruled out at the preoperative stage, lymph node dissection may be performed to prevent recurrence. Given the rarity of primary breast myxofibrosarcoma, there are no standardised treatment guidelines. Most therapeutic approaches are based on the principles of treating soft tissue sarcomas in other anatomical locations. Long-term follow-up of patients is essential, as local recurrences may occur even after complete surgical removal of the tumour.

Figure 3. Histopathological image showing spindle-shaped tumor cells arranged in intersecting fascicles within a myxoid stroma (H&E staining, ×100).

Figure 4. Proposed diagnostic algorithm for suspected primary breast sarcoma.

Table 1.

Reported cases of primary breast myxofibrosarcoma in the literature

Author	Year	Age	Tumor size	Treatment	Outcome
Thomas Mentzel et al.	1996	63	6 cm	Wide excision	No recurrence
Roberto Sanfilippo et al.	2011	58	8 cm	Mastectomy	Disease free
Suzanne Willems et al.	2019	71	5 cm	Wide excision	Local recurrence
Recent case reports	2020–2023	50–70	4–10 cm	Surgery ± RT	Variable
Present case (Uzbekistan)	2025	55	20 cm	Mastectomy + ALND	R0 resection

Conclusion. Primary mixed fibrosarcoma of the breast is an extremely rare malignant mesenchymal tumour with non-specific clinical symptoms and radiological features. As demonstrated in the present case, preoperative diagnosis can be challenging, and core needle biopsy may lead to misinterpretation due to the tumour's heterogeneous structure and morphological similarity to other spindle-cell lesions, such as desmoid fibromatosis or metaplastic carcinoma. Complete surgical resection of the tumour with negative resection margins remains the mainstay of treatment and the most important prognostic factor. Given the infiltrative nature of the growth and the high risk of local recurrence, thorough histopathological examination and long-term postoperative follow-up are essential. The presented clinical case highlights the importance of including rare sarcomas in the differential diagnosis of large spindle cell tumours of the breast and makes a further contribution to the limited body of literature on the clinical course and surgical management of primary mixofibrosarcoma of the breast.

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